

Face3DBiomark: A LOW-COST SOLUTION TO COMPUTE 3D FACIAL BIOMARKERS FOR DIAGNOSING CONDITIONS WITH ASSOCIATED FACIAL DYSMORPHOLOGIES

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Low-cost

- Nowadays, diagnosis is based on **qualitative visual assessments** and simple anthropometric measurements.
- Image-based approaches rely on high end equipments.
- **Face3DBiomark** is a low-cost, multi-platform tool for capturing high quality 3D facial meshes and computing facial biomarkers.

Architecture

- Based on a smartphone **app** for facial capture + a **website** for clinical data registration.

- **Dedicated server** for mesh processing and automatic landmarking.
- Clinical metadata saved in **non-relational** database.

Protocol

- Acquisition time of **10 seconds** approximately at a distance of **25-30cm**.

TrueDepth

- Facial point-cloud acquired via **iPhone TrueDepth camera** and Standard Cyborg API.
- **30.000** infrared dots are projected onto the face.

3D mesh

- Point-clouds processed with **PyMeshLab** for facial segmentation and orientation normalisation.
- Point-cloud **remeshing** using the Screened Poisson method.

Landmarks

- Facial landmarks automatically registered with **Multi-view consensus CNN**.
- Model trained with 538 manually landmarked facial 3D models from MRI.
- Mean error of less than **2 mm** compared to manual landmarks, **comparable** to that of an **expert morphologist**.

Biomarkers

- **GPA** and **EDMA** biomarkers identify statistically significant global and local differences in facial morphology.

Methodology

